

THE EMERGENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF GENDER IN THE LITERATURE AND SAD FATE OF EARLY FEMINISTS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the emergence of the concept of gender in the literature and the factors that led to this. The article also examines how similar the fates of Jeanne d'Arc and Nodirabegim were. Not only their fates differed, but also the goals on the path of freedom, justice and the well-being of their society, and these two were the first feminists of their time. One is now a national hero of France and a symbol of freedom in Western literature, and the second Nodirabegim is considered a defender of science and a poet of Uzbek classical literature. The article considers that the oppressed and untimely dead at the hands of the tyrants of their time are historical figures who today have earned an exceptional reputation, having reached the level of national heroes.*

Key words: *Gender, feminism, feminist, society, power, strength, freedom, enlightenment, justice, oppressor, oppressed, poet, saint.*

The world literature has paid special attention to gender issues for many years, as a consequence, different images have appeared in various cultures, as well as their nature has gradually changed. In this regard, it should be mentioned that the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century became extremely crucial, because socio-cultural changes occurred in the management of personal society in many countries, and it became noticeable that each country accepted the issue of gender equality in their own way. In this article, it is intended to pay special attention to the fact that gender appeared as a unique phenomenon in modern literature at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century.

In general, the concept of gender should be accepted as related to a certain group, class, category [1:123]. However, this explanation does not fully reveal this concept, according to the "Encyclopedia of the World: Philosophy" publication, in social sciences that study the socio-cultural aspect, it is emphasized that the sexual origin of a person depends on it [2:

221]. There is a sufficient deficiency in this view, that is, it indicates that a person's behavior in society and their relations are determined based on his gender, and this theory also loses its optimality due to the lack of complete clarity in this view. Gender is a concept based on the product of human activity, which led society to pay attention to its biological sex, and it consists of a collection of several opinions in this regard [3: 16]. However, it is better not to rely on the characteristics of views formed over the centuries on the basis of common views in the society, but rather to accept men and women as equal members of the human society, and think in literary studies based on the normative foundations of their behavior. The concept of gender in general is interpreted culturally and socially differently by many societies and is based mainly on the symbols of women and men. (For example, if creativity, light, power, activity, intelligence are considered masculine symbols; nature, obedience, weakness, feebleness, darkness, emptiness and confusion are considered feminine). Psychologist and Doctor of Philosophy in Feminist Perspectives Sandra Bem, while studying the problems associated with the acceptance of the concept of gender by the society, admits that it consists of a set of views that have arisen at the expense of social and cultural norms, which, in her opinion, are more important than a person's sexual origin, emphasizing that it is related to the attempt to own power in society [4: 281].

At first, the concept of Gender began to be recognized within the field of linguistics, and it was used as a grammatical term in the English language. Starting in 1958, Robert Stoller, a psychoanalyst at the University of California, Los Angeles, began to use it widely in his scientific views and explored the scope of the term. But only by 1963, this word began to be widely used. In this regard, at the congress of psychoanalysts held in Stockholm, R. Stoller stated that the concept of gender should be used not only to recognize biological characteristics, but also to take into account social and cultural aspects [5:8].

Despite the fact that this view has recently appeared, it is no secret that it is a social problem that has existed since the beginning of mankind. When studying the philosophy or literature of antiquity, the concept of gender consisted only of views related to physical and sexual origin: a woman was considered by nature to be extremely weak and even a representative of the lower class of society, therefore her role in society was limited only to giving birth to children; besides giving birth to children, a woman had to obey her husband unconditionally and do household chores. We found it appropriate to quote the words of the famous orator Demosthenes here:

"We take mistresses for presence, maids for care, wives for giving birth to legitimate children and loyalty to our household" [6:27].

Plato in one of his "the Symposium", as well as in the treatise "The Government", while Commenting on the city and the state in the treatise "the Government"; the philosopher stated men and women should have equal rights and put forward the idea that people should lead an independent life regardless of their sexual origin [7]. Because in ancient times, women's duties were limited only by the walls of the house, they had to be engaged only in housework. In Western society, the church played a major role in creating this situation. In its treatises, the Church asserts that the woman (Eve) is only a part of Adam, separated from the intellectual and spiritual side, an emotional complement. And such views in the society completely distanced the woman from the man, and the acceptance of women as beings who think with their heart and not with their mind grew stronger, and their influence in society also decreased. Such views exist not only in the culture of the West, but also in the culture of the Eastern society, for example, "Long hair, short mind", "A dog is faithful, a wife is jealous", "A stupid man interferes with a woman's speech", etc. represent the result of being viewed with.

From the information in the book "The Hammer of Witches", it can be understood that Western society believes that women are more likely to practice witchcraft than men. A woman is evil by nature and rejects any religion. [8]. As a result of such views, in the history of the Middle Ages, women were perceived by society as witches who practice black magic and spread evil, as well as being burned alive at the stake, falling to the level of evil spirit or female demon.

In this regard, considered the national hero of France with the fate of seventeen-year-old innocent girl Joan of Arc, who fought for the freedom of her country with her call "I will call all of you to the Court in front of the Creator!" and was finally accused of witchcraft and burned at the stake,

shows how such views were rampant in the Middle Ages [9]. The fate of the girl who fought for the freedom of her country made a big turn in the series

of historical events and caused the creation of such an immortal, national

image in French literature.

The best examples written about a feminist woman are A. "Saint Joan of Arc" by Vita Sackville, "Memoirs by Sieur Louis de Conte, Servant and Secretary of Joan of Arc" by Mark Twain, D. S. Merezhkovsky's "Joan of Arc",

"Joan of Arc" by Poturcin Maria Josefa Kurk von, O. M. Guryan's "Witnesses", P. V. The famous "Male Dress of Joan of Arc" by Krylov; V. "Joan of Arc" by Tropeiko, A. Deco's "Great Riddles History", a number of historical works such as Veleyco's "Jeanne the Slandered" and Bernard Shaw's "Saint Joan"

(Saint Joan - 1923) historical novels, short stories and essays are among them. Reading the fate of one of Europe's leading feminists, Jeanne, 15 doctors of theology, 4 doctors of ecclesiastical law and jurisprudence, 1 doctor of jurisprudence, 7 Bachelor of Theology and 4 High School Civil Rights students attended and filed 70 charges against a 17-year-old girl [10:48].

We intend to mention some of that charges which were announced by the ecclesiastic faculty of the University of Paris:

- 1) Joan's hearing the words of angels and saints is just a fiction or they come from the evil forces of the devil;
- 2) An angel bringing a crown to King Charles is also a lie and a claim to angelhood;
- 3) Joan is naive, thinks that it is easy to recognize saints with extreme lightness;
- 4) Joan is superstitious and overconfident, thinks that she can predict the future and believes that she knows people she has never met in her life;
- 5) Joan violated the divine law by wearing men's clothing;
- 6) She encourages that enemies can be defeated, but insists that she is doing so in the name of the Creator;
- 7) A girl who went against her parents' will and left home broke the biblical laws;
- 8) attempted to escape by jumping from Borevoir tower is actually considered a suicide due to depression.
- 9) The view that if one lives in honor of Joan, she will go directly to heaven, is foolishness and completely out of proportion to the foundations of religion.
- 10) Her claims that she spoke to the saints in French is considered disrespectful to the saints, or an attempt to imply that they were not on the side of the English, and it went against the scriptures about treating loved ones with love.
- 11) She is a pagan who invited demons.

12) Joan refused to trust the Church's court, especially in matters of confession.

In this way, Joan signed the charges, which could be a pardon for her, and the girl was spared the punishment of being burned alive at the stake, but they had no intention of keeping her alive. When she signed the charge sheet, she was again put in men's clothes, and the girl had no choice but to wear them. This inevitably led to the death penalty. Joan felt cheated and wore that dress without fear of going straight to death.

The girl was thus burned at the stake on May 30, 1431. Long after Joan's death, the liberation wars continued, and as a result, in the early 1450s, according to Joan's prophecies, which were considered fiction and superstition, Charles VII really sat on the throne of France and was crowned [11].

We also have many heroes who rose to the level of national heroes and put forward the first feminist views, the characters of Barchinoy and Kaldirgoch in the epic "Alpomish" in the Uzbek folklore are actually considered to be a symbol of historical figures like To'maris.

It must be admitted that the fate of Nodirabegim, who was considered the enlightened poet of Uzbek classical literature, was even more terrible than the fate of Joan of Arc. These two historical figures can easily be called oppressed feminists who fell victim to oppressors for the great goal of freedom and social justice. It is to the society that they do not lag behind men in their sanity and aspirations

because they were able to show, they died needlessly at the hands of the oppressors who were in the hands of power and authority. It is known that in 1842 Nadirabegim was executed by the emir of Bukhara, Nasrullah Khan, together with his two children and a 14-year-old grandson. [12]. It should be said that ignorance and enlightenment collided in the form of Nadirabegim and Nasrullah. Nadirabegim, who was a forward-thinking intellectual of her time, naturally hated the emir, who worked for the well-being of the nation and justice. Therefore, the emir considered Nodirabegim as one of his most dangerous enemies in the Kokan Khanate. But Nasrullah Khan could not directly execute the poet. Therefore, he tried to use as a basis the mistakes of Muhammad Ali Khan, who lost his way, for the incident of execution.

After the death of his father Umar Khan in 1822, Muhammad Ali Khan, who ascended the throne, began to manage the power together with his mother. But he did not follow his mother's path. Muhammad Ali Khan's enemies, who managed to gain enough wealth in a short period of time,

spreaded incitement about him saying, "He married his stepmother while having two biological sisters." As a result, Muhammadali Khan was severely accused. Actually, Khanposhshaoyim was not Muhammadali Khan's stepmother. Although she was one of the concubines in the court of Amir Umar Khan, Amir Umar Khan passed away before she came of age.

So, the ambassador of Bukhara in Kokone, Muhammad Ali Khan, brought the fatwa declaring him an infidel to Emir Nasrullah. A battle began between the emir of Bukhara and the Khan of Kokan. The amir who won the battle transferred the cities of Oratepa, Karachukum and Kokan to Sultan Mahmud Khan, the second son of Nodirabegim. Due to Muhammadali Khan's next mistakes, another rebellion will rise in Kokan. At the time of Amir Nasrullah's invasion of Kokhan, Muhammadali Khan was not a khan, but an ordinary citizen. After the first invasion of the emir, in November 1841, he completely abdicated the throne and handed over the khanate to his brother Sultan Mahmud Khan.

The pretext for Muhammadali Khan's execution was the fatwa declaring him an infidel. This fatwa was indeed a sufficient basis in the eyes of the people for the execution of Muhammad Ali Khan and the acquisition of his beautiful wife and other goals. A question arises here. And his logical answer clarifies the story. Muhammad Ali Khan was declared an infidel in 1841. After that, Amir attacked Kokan for the first time. So, since Muhammad Ali Khan was an infidel, why was he executed exactly six months later without being punished at that time? So, Nasrullah Khan came to Kokan one time, but several times. Nodirabegim was the only enemy who could prevent his goals.

While her eldest son is being executed, Amir waited for Nadirabegim to be in agony and cry weakly. However, according to Mutrib, Nadirabegim, who was "a hundred times better in terms of bravery and nobility", did not cry out despite the fact that she is suffering terribly. Seeing this, the prince sentenced the second son of the poetess to death. According to Mutrib's work "Shahnomai Devona Mutrib", when the young and promising prince Sultan Mahmud Khan begged for mercy from the executioners, even the executioners had tears in their eyes.

Nodirabegim became insane after the execution of her second child. Nasrullah was waiting for his mother to faint and scream. It was not as what he expected.

Enraged by this, the emir ordered the execution of Nodirabegim's 14-year-old grandson Muhammad Amin Khan. Finally, She cried out...

She curses the emir by telling him all his evil deeds. She chose death instead of ointment for her endless pains.

Conclusion: Joan saw that she was not given any clothes except men's clothes in prison, she knew that if she wore them, she could inevitably die, and she felt that society and time condemned her to death, so she faced death. In this respect, her actions are still considered brave.

After all, she knew that inevitable death was waiting for her when she was going to fight, but fear was alien to the girl. She is celebrated as a hero who fought for the freedom of the nation and as a hero of the nation who made a turning point in the history of France, who managed to show that women had the vote for the first time, and who started the rebellion against the British oppression. what she expected.

Because her prophecies came true after her death, Joan was also given the status of a saint [13]. Today, in the West, Joan of Arc is a national hero, and those who executed the girl are eternally imprinted in the pages of history as traitors and conquerors. The unfair trial conducted against her, is recognized as the most shameful trial that brutally punished the girl.

Nadirabegim rebelled against violation with her last cry. Amir Nasrullah handed her over to the executioners to confirm the victory of ignorance, and the enlightened poet was executed for speaking out against ignorance. The killers used the poet's son Muhammad Ali Khan for this.

His beautiful wife Khanposhshaoyim also became an excuse for him. So, the emir of Bukhara, Nasrullah Khan, avenged the ignorance of the enlightened poet. But he was overcome, because enlightenment still triumphed over ignorance. These days, Nasrullah Khan remains in the past with the name of the butcher-emir, and his rule is recognized as the most cruel and bloody years in the history of the Bukhara Emirate, and the name of Nadirabegim is sealed as an enlightened poet.

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